

USE OF EDTECH TOOLS IN UKRAINIAN UNIVERSITIES DURING THE PERIOD OF ADAPTATION TO NEW REALITIES

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Abstract

The article analyzes the experience of using educational technologies for teaching a foreign language in times of emergency, including the period of pandemic and military conflict. The study focuses on a review of the use of various tools, and platforms Moodle, a Learning Management System (LMS), in particular, for continuing education in blended format. The results of the analysis show that the platform successfully promotes several aspects of English language teaching, such as online material delivery, interactive exercises, assessment tools, and communication. Challenges and difficulties of using Moodle in new realities, such as server overload and the increased teacher work overload are also highlighted. Moodle has been considered and recommended as a trusted tool for supporting the educational process and guaranteeing its continuity in challenging situations.

Keywords: educational technology, Moodle, teaching a foreign language, educational process, blended learning.

Introduction

The educational environment in Ukraine has been severely affected by emergencies, such as ongoing problems related to the COVID-19 pandemic and armed aggression. These challenges required a shift from traditional face-to-face learning to non-standard learning where technology has become a vital factor in ensuring education continuity. To adapt to these circumstances, teachers are increasingly relying on various tools of educational technology (EdTech) to support the teaching of English. Educational technologies in modern realities are transformed in the context of Ukrainian universities. Using digital tools and resources has made it possible to create an even more innovative, immersive, and interactive language learning environment.

Research into the use of educational technologies in teaching has a long tradition. For decades, one of the most popular ideas in the scientific and methodological literature has been that technology can significantly improve the quality of learning. Innovative solutions such as the use of artificial intelligence in education are becoming increasingly popular. However, the main problems are that not all approaches are equally effective and teachers are not adequately trained to use the latest tools. There is still a lack of comprehensive studies that would combine analysis of pedagogical effectiveness, technological accessibility, and students' perception of such technologies. There are several issues and gaps in the research of educational technologies. These include an overarching analysis of the effectiveness of digital tools in improving learning outcomes, research into transdisciplinary methods, adaptive technologies, and long-term effects. Teaching methods need to be redefined as technology moves from being a source of knowledge to a mediator in education.

The research purpose

This article aims to present a review of educational technologies that are successfully used in the practice of teaching foreign language in Ukrainian universities during emergencies.

Literature review

Adaptation of Ukrainian higher education institutions to new realities, including the transition to distance and blended learning, requires the introduction and effective use of educational technologies.

Deep and comprehensive understanding of the theory and practice of distance learning, transactional distance learning theory and its application in teaching (Moore, 2013), principles and methods of distance course design (Salmon, 2002) and the role of learner autonomy in distance learning (Siemens, 2006) is a key aspect in the implementation and use of technology in higher education. Models and approaches to active student engagement through electronic activities are of great interest to Ukrainian educators (Altukhova et al., 2022).

The need for changes in approaches to teaching and research in the context of digitalization and the impact of technology on academic practice is due to the availability of open educational resources (OER) on access to knowledge (Weller, 2011), the changing role of the scientist in the digital age, the potential of social networks for academic communication (Mykytiuk et al., 2020).

Emphasis on the importance of adapting teaching methods to the digital age: the need to develop flexible curricula, the importance of using multimedia resources to improve student-teacher interactions (Qadumi & Smith, 2024), the application of adaptive technologies to personalize learning (Bates, 2019), is especially relevant for Ukrainian universities in the period of change (Westerlund et al., 2023).

According to Terry Anderson, a professor at Athabasca University, to understand the characteristics of distance learning and ways to improve its effectiveness, a deep analysis of online education is needed - from the importance of interaction in online learning, models of a constructivist approach to online learning, to the use of technology to support pedagogical interactions.

Materials and Methods

The study was conducted in the academic year 2023-2024 at the Yaroslav Mudryi National Law University. The observation of the use of EdTech was made in the process of teaching applicants for higher education who attended the compulsory academic courses "Foreign Language" (Introduction to Legal English, Legal English, Academic English) online and offline.

For this study we examined various educational tools, in particular Moodle, to investigate the effectiveness of learning in terms of complex military environments.

The data was analyzed from different points of view such as convenience and efficiency on the one hand, and problems related to using educational tools on the other.

Results and Discussion

Since the pre-pandemic period, platforms like Zoom, Google Meet, and Microsoft Teams have become familiar with online lectures, group discussions, and interactive classes. These tools have helped recreate the dynamics of the physical audience, allowing students to interact with their teachers and colleagues in real-time, even from remote locations. Whereas in the present period, other sources already cover new digital technologies, such as virtual reality, augmented reality, game-like elements, Microsoft's Learning Tools, and Lifelong Learning Platforms, like Coursera (TOXIGON Infinite).

Let's turn to the analysis of the use of asynchronous platforms in this period of mixed learning in the process of teaching foreign language to students of Ukraine on the example of the Yaroslav Mudryi National Law University. These platforms have long proven themselves as reliable, along with synchronous learning. They allow students to access assignments, lecture materials, recorded podcasts, and sessions at their convenience, which is especially important for those students who face irregular schedules or communication problems. For example, students from conflict-affected regions can download materials during periods of stable internet connectivity and continue their education offline, thereby minimizing the risk of falling behind.

During the online learning period, as well as the transition to a mixed form, the question gradually arose of how to make English lessons interesting and interactive, for these teachers turned to tools such as Kahoot, Quizlet, and Mentimeter. These platforms are designed to engage students in learning through tests, surveys, and tasks while ensuring that students become more motivated. For example, vocabulary training can take place during a Kahoot game, where students compete to answer questions correctly. Quizlet allows students to create cards for memorizing and learning vocabulary, while Mentimeter can be used to conduct interactive surveys and provide feedback during live sessions.

Group tools such as Google Docs and Padlet have also become important in the development and improvement of language skills. These platforms allow students to work together on written projects and provide an opportunity for feedback and collaborative collective improvement. The group of students can create a presentation or written assignment in Google Docs, which will allow them to improve their grammar and text coherence by working together in real time.

Specialized language applications and platforms such as Duolingo, Grammarly, and BBC Learning English were well known long ago but successfully became even more widely used during the pandemic and war. These resources provide personalized practice to students, especially those in affected regions or for temporarily displaced persons. Ukrainian universities have shown resilience in providing high-quality English language learning in challenging times by tackling new challenges and integrating various existing EdTech tools.

The Moodle platform, which has been successfully used during a pandemic and military conflict period as a blended learning format tool, has many features available to support various learning purposes.

Let's define the Moodle functions that support learning English. Moodle offers elements or tools that facilitate the implementation of all aspects of learning English. For example, multimedia files and reading materials can be published online (Bates, 2021), modules areas such as SCORM packages for interactive content delivery, tests, and assignments for students' learning. To improve your listening and reading skills, you can download multimedia in the form of videos, audio files, and texts. Tests and exercises related to grammar, vocabulary, and writing are the most common applications. Other plugins, such as H5P, provide highly interactive exercises from blanking to cards. BigBlueButton, working with Moodle, is a videoconferencing tool for real-time interaction that allows you to practice speaking. In addition, instant feedback is possible through the automatic rating system. Moodle enables you to track student progress and utilize this data to concentrate on areas that require improvement (Manalo, 2021).

The greatest value of Moodle for language teaching is, in our opinion, its flexibility and accessibility. Students can access materials anytime, anywhere thanks to its mobile-friendly design. This allows them to take into account different schedules and learning rates, which is noted by many scientists (Anderson, 2008; Bates, 2021; Moore, 2013).

Using real-time communication tools, participants can also work together on group projects.

Moodle has become a proven platform in the process of teaching English at Ukrainian universities during emergencies. As a Universal Learning Management System (LMS), it allows teachers to create structured courses adapted to the needs of students. In times of emergency, the adaptability of Moodle has proved invaluable, especially for teaching English. Teachers could develop and download vocabulary and grammar tests, interactive reading assignments, or essay assign-

ments that can be automatically graded. Moodle supports a tool like Turnitin, which is important for testing for artificial intelligence and anti-plagiarism.

Students in regions where internet access is limited can download course materials and complete assignments without constant connection with the offline accessibility features of Moodle during this time period. This flexibility ensures that students can continue to develop their English language skills regardless of the circumstances. In Ukrainian universities, Moodle has become a crucial tool that assists in overcoming the challenges of urgent learning.

Experience of using this tool in e-learning has shown that Moodle (platform) successfully adapted to the discipline «Foreign Language»: combined storage of electronic learning materials, and also provided the

opportunity for interactive communication between teacher and student.

The main advantages of Moodle in the current realities in Ukrainian universities are: accessible and ergonomic interface; structure of electronic learning materials that are uploaded to Moodle and stored there, can be modified and constantly modified, depending on the needs of the training process, there is also the possibility to use additional modules for functional expansion. Moodle has a large variety of course elements and resources: Video conference BigBlueButton, Glossary, Quiz, Interactive content, Lecture, Feedback, Survey, Seminar, Test (various types), Forum, Chat, Hyperlink, Book, Folder, Comment, Page, File etc. are shown in Figure 1.

Figure 1. Moodle elements and resources.

Figures 2, 3 and 4 demonstrate different content of courses «Foreign Language» on Moodle using different

resources and elements, depending on the specialty/specialization, curriculum and course of the applicants of higher education.

Figure 2. Lesson for first-year bachelor's students.

Figure 3. Lesson for second-year master's students.

Figure 4. Lesson for postgraduate students.

We will also name the following as advantages of Moodle in teaching foreign languages: the ability to continuously monitor the activities of both the teacher and the student; the presence of an integrated editor; the ability to remotely assess students in automatic mode; the absence of spam; the ability to send messages, grades and comments to an email address; the ability to set deadlines for completing assignments, etc.

Let's look at Moodle's capabilities for assessing English language skills in more detail. Moodle is a universal platform for evaluating learning outcomes across different aspects of the language. Teachers can create multiple-choice tasks to test active vocabulary, grammar, or synonym recognition, fill-in-the-gaps exercises to practice vocabulary and sentence structure, and definition-matching questions. The test can include randomization features, ensuring that students receive different sets of questions, which is necessary to maintain academic integrity when working remotely.

Moodle is ideal for assessing writing skills. Students submit their work directly through Moodle, allowing the teacher to annotate the work using a PDF editor, and provide feedback using text comments. Huerta-Gomez-Merodio and Requena-García-Cruz (2024) discussed the impact of advanced plugins such as FastTest on streamlining the assessment process, allowing teachers to focus on providing meaningful feedback.

To assess listening skills, you can develop and upload tests based on attached audio or video recordings. To assess speaking skills, there are tools such as the audio recording plugin that allow you to assess pronunciation, fluency, and coherence. However, these features cannot demonstrate the authenticity and integrity of the task.

Moodle allows students to evaluate each other's work based on agreed criteria. Self-assessment functions encourage students to identify their strengths and

areas for improvement. According to some researchers, the integration of such tools into Moodle has led to more dynamic and interactive assessment methods (Huerta-Gomez-Merodio & Requena-Garcia-Cruz, 2024).

The Moodle gradebook can combine results, giving teachers a clear view of each student's performance. The grading scale and organization of categories make it possible to track and analyze student progress across different skills, such as speaking, writing, or grammar. This centralized view allows for targeted support to be provided to struggling students (Huerta-Gomez-Merodio & Requena-Garcia-Cruz, 2024).

The Moodle system has proven to be useful in that teachers can set up assignments so that they can be viewed by other students. Teachers can comment on students' work or upload their own comments. This feature is particularly useful for assessing written assignments such as essays, allowing suggestions for improving grammar, coherence and vocabulary. As mentioned, Moodle's gradebook feature brings all student performance data together in one place. Thus, individual progress can be analyzed and learning gaps identified, and methodological strategies changed and adjusted accordingly. It should be noted that with the recent trend towards large numbers of students in groups, working in Moodle helps ensure that no student is left without material or ungraded. In emergencies where continuous monitoring is difficult, Moodle's advanced assessment capabilities can be of great help.

In turn, it is possible to note a number of disadvantages of Moodle, as well as problems that arose in the process of distance teaching of English. During the period of mass e-learning, which was implemented during the COVID-19 pandemic, the Moodle platform proved to be a rather demanding product for the server and during high server loads it failed to work. It should also be noted that the teacher's workload in the e-learning format is much higher in terms of time costs, since it takes a lot of time to create high-quality and methodologically correct content, and also that distance learning requires high motivation from the student. And sometimes excessive reliance on digital tools can lead to less interaction during face-to-face sessions (Manalo, 2021).

The practice of introducing e-learning has shown that not all students are capable of self-discipline and self-organization; - there is a certain problem in proving the authenticity of the learning results. It is almost impossible for the teacher to determine that a student has done the task himself, whether it be a test or a written assignment.

In general, the experience of using the Moodle platform in the process of teaching and learning in the discipline "Foreign Language" at Yaroslav Mudryi National Law University can be characterized as positive. The use of this virtual educational platform in a blended learning format is an effective and promising tool for developing students' language competencies.

Conclusion

Educational technologies, and especially the Moodle platform, have proven to be important tools for teaching English at Ukrainian universities during the emergency. Its diverse functions for teaching, sharing,

assessment, feedback, and monitoring have enabled teachers to cope with the challenges of the time and the problems associated with distance learning. The platform's many features support a holistic approach to education, from the ability to upload and store materials, testing and dynamic peer assessments to comprehensive analytics and accessibility features. By ensuring the continuity of education, the platform's capabilities have provided significant support to both teachers and students during this new time.

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